

VATARAKTA AS DOSHA -DHATU PERSPECTIVE***¹Dr. Aakanksha Singh, ²Dr. Nikhila Ranjan Nayak, ³Dr. Febin Paul Jose**¹PG Scholar, Roga Nidana Evam Vikriti Vigyan, Shri NPA, Gov. Ayurved College, Raipur.²Professor & HOD of Roga Nidana Evam Vikriti Vigyan, Gov. Ayurved College, Raipur.³Associate Professor (Reader) Department of Panchakarma Gov. Ayurved College, Raipur.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Aakanksha Singh**

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ABSTRACT

Vatarakta, described in detail across the Brhat-trayi, is a disorder arising from the simultaneous vitiation of Vata dosha and Rakta dhatu. And considered a prime example of avarana janya vyadhi, where mutual obstruction occurs between the two. When Vata becomes aggravated by its nidanas and Rakta is vitiated by pitta-increasing or Rakta-dusti- causing factors, shows a progressive pathogenesis that moves from the superficial Uttana to deep Gambhira stage. Its description corresponds closely to modern 'gout'. At first it confirms its root in hands and feet and then spread all over the body. This article explains Vatarakta through the lens of dosha-dhatu involvement, highlighting the dynamics of vitiation, obstruction, srotas involvement, circulation disturbance, tissue pathology. The aim is to establish a comprehensive understanding of Vatarakta as a systemic disease rooted in dosa-dhatu conflict.

KEYWORDS: Vatarakta, Doshā-Dhatu Samgraha, Vata-Rakta Avarana, Uttana and Gambhira Vatarakta, gout.**INTRODUCTION**

Vatarakta is a type of Vatavyadhi. The detail description is scattered in all classical literature extensively. Due to intake of diet consisting of salty, sour, pungent alkaline, fatty, hot and uncooked articles, moist or dried things, meat of aquatic and marshy animals, journey on carts carried by horses and camel, etc the aggravated Vata have been obstructed in its passage by aggravated blood affects the entire blood this is known as Vatarakta. It is caused mainly by excessively aggravated Vata and Rakta in associated with other Dosha which mostly affects the extremities & leads to connective tissue disorders & peripheral vascular disorders Vata- dosha and Rakta-dhatu.

Vatarakta is a chronic joint & body pain diseases accompanied by pain stiffness, swelling over joints, Which involve vitiated Vatadosha as well as Raktadhatu aggravated, Vata is blocked by vitiated Rakta, Which lead to future aggravation of Vata dosha.

Vatarakta 2 awasthas – Uttana & Gambhira.

Uttana Vatarakta affects Twacha & Mansadhatu whereas Gambhira mainly affects asthi, majjadi gambhira dhatu.

It is correlated with "Gout" – It is a metabolic disease caused by the deposition of monosodium urate crystals inside joints, characterized by pain and swelling of first metatarsophalangeal joints initially, other common site are the ankle, midfoot, knee, small joint of hands, wrist and elbow.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Literary sources

The present conceptual review is based on an indepth study of classical Ayurvedic texts including:

- Charaka Samhita-Chikitsa sthana 29
- Sushruta Samhita -Nidana sthana 1, Chikitsa Sthana-4
- Astanga Hrdaya – Nidana 17, chikitsa 19.

METHODOLOGY

- Identification of nidana, samprapti, lakshana, and bheda of Vatarakta.
- Analysis of Vata prakopa and Rakta dusti independently and conjointly
- Evaluation of disease progression from Uttana (superficial) to Gambhira (deep seated) stages

- Interpretation through the lens of Dosha- dhatu interaction.

NIDANA OF VATARAKTA

In *Ayurved*, the causative factors (Nidana) of Vatarakta are categorized under Aaharaj (dietary causes) and Viharaja (lifestyle causes).

Aaharaj Nidana (dietary causes) include

- By consuming foods, which produce burning sensation at the time of digestion, which are prohibited combinations or processes.
- Excessive intake of Rasa such as Katu, Tikta, Kshaya, Amla, Lavana and Kshara.
- Excessive consumption of Ahara that is Snighda, Ushna, Ruksha, and Klina.
- Alcoholic drinks, sour substances, buttermilk, meat of aquatic animals and such others are vidahi substances.
- The habit of taking Viruddha Aahara (incomplete diet), Adhyashana (intake of food prior to digestion of meal earlier taken).
- Intake of Anupa Mamsa, kulathika, Masha, Nishpava, Sura and Aasava etc

Viharaja Nidana include

- Abhigata (trauma)
- Krodha (anger)
- Divaswapna (daytime sleep)
- Raatrijagrana (staying awake during the night)
- Achankramansheelata (lack of physical activity)
- Plavan (swimming)
- Veganigraha (suppression of natural urges)
- Traveling on Hasti, Ashva, Usthra.

Purvarupa

The premonitory symptoms of Vatarakta are similar to those of kustha, in addition are found, weakness, looseness of body parts, itching, throbbing, severe breaking and splitting pain, feeling of heaviness and numbness of the joints of forelegs.

Rupa

This disease localises its root in the feet and sometimes in the hands and then spreads all over the body just like poison of the bite of rat.

Uttana Vatarakta- Involvement limited to twak and mamsa.

Symptoms: Kandu, daha, sphurana, mild sotha, coppery red, black or red colour, and it is spread over, has severe burning sensation and heat.

Predominance of Rakta dusti with superficial Vata involvement.

Gambhira Vatarakta- Involvement of deeper dhatus: rakta, mamsa, asthi, majja.

Symptoms: Severe pain, stabdhata, sandhi vikriti, vaivarnya, swelling, nodular and ulceration, Vata spreads

with great speed in the joints, bones and marrow, creating cutting pain and curves.

Dominant Vata prakopa with profound dhatu ksaya.

Gout (Inflammatory Arthritis)

Samprapti of Vatarakta

The core event in Vatarakta is Avarana of Vata by Rakta.

Nidana Sewan (Rakta prakopaka & Vata prakopka)

Vata Dosha-The primary dosha (Dominant Dosa)

Vata plays the leading role in Vatarakta. In Ayurvedic texts Vata is the most significant among Tridoshas. Due to its sixfold distinguishing features like *Ruksha*, *Laghu*, *Sheeta*, *Khara*, *Chala*, *Sukshama* gunas, The unvitiated Vayu maintains the equilibrium between dosas, dhatus and metabolic fire and helps in the perception of objects of senses by inducing the systems to function in their normal ways. Its aggravation can occur due to fasting, irregular food habits, excessive exertion, exposure to cold etc.

Role of Vata in Pathogenesis

1. Pravritt (abnormal movement) - Aggravated Vata becomes excessively mobile and enters various tissues, disturbing normal circulation.
2. Ruksata(dryness)- Dries the channels (srotas) and narrows them, increasing the risk of blockage.
3. Suksma guna- Allows Vata to carry vitiated Rakta into smaller capillaries and deeper tissues.
4. Vyana Vata involvement- Disturbs peripheral circulation, leading to pain, discoloration, and altered temperature.

Clinical feature of Vata

- Severe pricking or throbbing pain.
- Stiffness and restricted movement.

- Dryness of skin or joints.

Rakta as a Dosa-like Entity (Primary Dhatu)

Rakta is the first and most affected dhatu, it is a well-known fact that the life of living beings absolutely depends on Rakta.

Factors vitiating Rakta

- Alcohol.
- Salt, sour, pungent foods.
- Excess heat exposure.
- Incompatible and contaminated food.
- Anger and emotional disturbance.

Clinical feature of Rakta

- Swelling with severe distress and piercing pain
- Pricking sensation
- Itching & moistening.

Upadrava

- Sandhi Vikriti
- Chronic inflammation and deformity.
- Difficulty in walking

Sadhyasadhya

Vatarakra, caused by one dosa and of recent origin is curable. That caused by two dosas is maintainable. Vatarakta produced by three dosas and having discharges, inertness and tendency to cause arbuda should be rejected.

Chikitsa (Treatment)

Nidana Parivarjana - Avoidance of Rakta and Vata vitiating factors is essential.

Sodhana chikitsa - Raktamoksana (Siravedha, jalauka) - prime treatment.

Virechana- especially in Rakta pradosaja conditions

Basti- for Vata samana

Samana chikitsa – Kasaya and Tikta rasa pradhana drugs

Guduchi, Manjistha, Nimba, Sariva

Guggulu preparations in chronic stages.

Pathya-Apathya

Pathya- Sheeta, laghu, tikta ahara, ghrta.

Apathya- Lavana, amla, madya, dadhi, mamsa

DISCUSSION

From the classical Ayurvedic viewpoints, Vatarakta is a clinical state arising from the simultaneous vitiation of Vata and Rakta, with reciprocal obstruction (avarana) between them. The condition highlights a complex interaction of dosa dynamics, dhatu disturbances, srotas involvement, and agni-ama pathology.

Dosha Interaction- The primary dosa is Vata, commonly triggered by

- Excessive ruksha, sita, laghu, factors
- Overexertion

- Fasting
- Aging

Rakta dosa become vitiated through.

- Intake of amla, lavana, katu aahar
- Alcohol
- Exposure to heat
- Anger and stress

Dhatu Involvement- The main dhatu affected is Rakta, but also involves Mamsa, Meda, and Asthi.

Vatarakta first starts as *Uttana* type by taking seat in the skin and muscular tissue and in due course it becomes *gambhira* type, spreading to all dhatus.

CONCLUSION

Vatarakta, when viewed through the dosa-dhatu framework, emerges as a systemic inflammatory - metabolic disorder rooted in Vata-Rakta imbalance. The pathology originates in the dual vitiation of Vata and Rakta, progresses through avarana mechanisms, and gradually spreads from superficial to deeper dhatus. This integrated perspective helps explain the condition's acute flares, chronic stiffness, deformity, and metabolic associations. As the disease migrates across dhatus-from Rakta to Tvak, Mamsa, Meda, and Asthi-it transforms from a superficial inflammatory condition to a deep-seated metabolic and degenerative pathology. The evolution reflects deeper involvement of agni, ama, srotas, and dhatu-ksaya, ultimately causing chronic disability if untreated.

This perspective emphasizes that successful management must not merely reduce symptoms but address.

- Vata pacification,
- Rakta purification,
- Dhatu restoration,
- Agni rekindling,
- Srotas clearance,
- Prevention of dhatu ksaya.

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